

Inflammatory proteins associated with primary osteoarthritis outco	
id	pvalue
GCST90274765	0.000581255
GCST90274769	0.015908194
GCST90274772	0.028510664
GCST90274787	0.005961538
GCST90274801	0.006745419
GCST90274815	0.010344334
GCST90274817	0.002875605
GCST90274837	0.020313419
GCST90274843	0.010822948
GCST90274844	0.03307094

Cytokines	nS N P	Beta	P	Or	Or(95%CI)	Q_pval	Steig er_pval	MR- PRES SO_p val	MR Egger _pval
C-C motif chemokine 19							6E-04	0.728	0.15
MR Egger	36	-0.15	0.00201	0.861	0.789-0.940	0.04			
Weighted median	36	-0.129	0.00039	0.879	0.818-0.944				
Inverse variance weighted	36	-0.098	0.00058	0.906	0.857-0.959	0.027			
Simple mode	36	-0.154	0.01786	0.857	0.759-0.968				
Weighted mode	36	-0.142	#####	0.868	0.815-0.923				
C-C motif chemokine 28							0.016	0.558	0.346
MR Egger	37	0.02	0.781	1.02	0.888-1.171	0.55			
Weighted median	37	0.105	0.0301	1.11	1.010-1.222				
Inverse variance weighted	37	0.079	0.0159	1.08	1.015-1.155	0.554			
Simple mode	37	0.098	0.3617	1.1	0.896-1.357				
Weighted mode	37	0.072	0.3967	1.07	0.912-1.266				
CD40L receptor							0.029	0.143	0.309
MR Egger	23	0.032	0.4131	1.03	0.958-1.113	0.052			
Weighted median	23	0.032	0.2267	1.03	0.981-1.087				
Inverse variance weighted	23	0.06	0.0285	1.06	1.006-1.121	0.047			
Simple mode	23	0.155	0.0799	1.17	0.990-1.378				
Weighted mode	23	0.033	0.2342	1.03	0.980-1.091				
Fibroblast growth factor 19							0.006	0.159	0.66
MR Egger	33	-0.06	0.4831	0.94	0.808-1.105	0.148			
Weighted median	33	-0.04	0.3805	0.96	0.876-1.052				
Inverse variance weighted	33	-0.09	0.006	0.91	0.858-0.975	0.172			
Simple mode	33	-0.02	0.8466	0.98	0.815-1.182				
Weighted mode	33	0.005	0.9421	1	0.889-1.135				
Interleukin-17A							0.007	0.03	0.517
MR Egger	19	0.072	0.5	1.07	0.876-1.317	0.023			
Weighted median	19	0.085	0.144	1.09	0.971-1.220				
Inverse variance weighted	19	0.132	0.0067	1.14	1.037-1.256	0.027			
Simple mode	19	0.087	0.4419	1.09	0.878-1.355				
Weighted mode	19	0.029	0.7453	1.03	0.866-1.223				
Interleukin-6 levels							0.01	0.593	0.473
MR Egger	13	0.059	0.5025	1.06	0.898-1.253	0.502			
Weighted median	13	0.076	0.2019	1.08	0.960-1.213				
Inverse variance weighted	13	0.113	0.0103	1.12	1.027-1.221	0.54			
Simple mode	13	0.118	0.2419	1.13	0.932-1.358				
Weighted mode	13	0.07	0.2872	1.07	0.948-1.213				
Interleukin-8							0.003	0.385	0.559
MR Egger	31	-0.07	0.2807	0.93	0.827-1.055	0.299			
Weighted median	31	-0.07	0.1629	0.94	0.854-1.027				
Inverse variance weighted	31	-0.1	0.0029	0.91	0.849-0.967	0.328			
Simple mode	31	-0.07	0.3764	0.93	0.796-1.088				
Weighted mode	31	-0.05	0.3821	0.95	0.839-1.068				
STAM binding protein							0.02	0.569	0.725
MR Egger	20	-0.06	0.5629	0.94	0.764-1.155	0.472			
Weighted median	20	-0.13	0.0289	0.88	0.781-0.987				
Inverse variance weighted	20	-0.1	0.0203	0.91	0.837-0.985	0.53			
Simple mode	20	-0.14	0.1712	0.87	0.723-1.052				

Weighted mode	20	-0.13	0.1718	0.88	0.740-1.049				
TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand							0.011	0.025	0.01
MR Egger	36	-0.06	0.1877	0.95	0.871-1.026	0.008			
Weighted median	36	-0.07	0.026	0.93	0.880-0.992				
Inverse variance weighted	36	-0.06	0.0108	0.94	0.894-0.986	0.01			
Simple mode	36	-0.05	0.4259	0.95	0.851-1.070				
Weighted mode	36	-0.06	0.0796	0.94	0.887-1.005				
TNF-related activation-induced cytokine							0.033	0.804	0.446
MR Egger	47	0.104	0.091	1.11	0.986-1.248	6E-04			
Weighted median	47	0.051	0.1585	1.05	0.980-1.129				
Inverse variance weighted	47	0.064	0.0331	1.07	1.005-1.130	7E-04			
Simple mode	47	0.033	0.654	1.03	0.894-1.196				
Weighted mode	47	-0	0.9695	1	0.915-1.089				

C-C motif chemokine 19

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(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

C-C motif chemokine 28

C-C motif chemokine 28

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

CD40L receptor

CD40L receptor

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Fibroblast growth factor 19

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(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Interleukin-17A

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Interleukin-6

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Interleukin-8

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

STAM binding protein

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

TNF-related activation-induced cytokine

TNF-related activation-induced cytokine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand

TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Inflammatory proteins associated with plasma metabolite outcome id		
immfatorid	plasma metabolite	pvalue
GCST90274765	GCST90200160	0.015418118
GCST90274765	GCST90200170	0.022656988
GCST90274765	GCST90200374	0.013387865
GCST90274765	GCST90200381	0.041380177
GCST90274765	GCST90200384	0.005527616
GCST90274765	GCST90200385	0.02658975
GCST90274765	GCST90200333	0.030178057
GCST90274765	GCST90200403	0.021684537
GCST90274765	GCST90200616	0.011726887
GCST90274765	GCST90200592	0.030643336
GCST90274765	GCST90200605	0.023541177
GCST90274765	GCST90200613	0.019532905
GCST90274765	GCST90200189	0.038020529
GCST90274765	GCST90200206	0.048020152
GCST90274765	GCST90200208	0.017478154
GCST90274765	GCST90200248	0.00644677
GCST90274765	GCST90200264	0.040378899
GCST90274765	GCST90200266	0.018816123
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GCST90274765	GCST90200277	0.046404401
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GCST90274765	GCST90200074	0.025312656
GCST90274765	GCST90200647	0.02935322
GCST90274765	GCST90200652	0.002760852
GCST90274765	GCST90200660	0.041355598
GCST90274765	GCST90199960	0.008924919
GCST90274765	GCST90199961	0.042248327
GCST90274765	GCST90200012	0.018622382
GCST90274765	GCST90201000	0.038397572
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GCST90274765	GCST90201012	0.046154591
GCST90274765	GCST90201017	0.018040697
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GCST90274765	GCST90199716	0.043305876
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GCST90274765	GCST90199729	0.001233655
GCST90274765	GCST90200212	0.004460865
GCST90274765	GCST90200221	0.044029907
GCST90274765	GCST90199684	0.030458422
GCST90274765	GCST90199685	0.029365979
GCST90274765	GCST90200209	0.00662733
GCST90274765	GCST90199896	0.02233676
GCST90274765	GCST90199927	0.034883968
GCST90274765	GCST90200041	0.017837295

GCST90274765	GCST90200564	0.028189909
GCST90274765	GCST90200572	0.015096662
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GCST90274765	GCST90200766	0.006589495
GCST90274765	GCST90200748	0.006015094
GCST90274765	GCST90200754	0.025268677
GCST90274765	GCST90200758	0.01212044
GCST90274765	GCST90200761	0.006324567
GCST90274765	GCST90199800	0.025236908
GCST90274765	GCST90199759	0.043316384
GCST90274765	GCST90200531	0.047903194
GCST90274765	GCST90200501	0.017961292
GCST90274765	GCST90200516	0.020200307
GCST90274765	GCST90200672	0.025864177
GCST90274765	GCST90200305	0.00984877
GCST90274765	GCST90200315	0.032026303
GCST90274765	GCST90200322	0.000790149
GCST90274765	GCST90200453	0.013164084
GCST90274765	GCST90200500	0.044110314
GCST90274765	GCST90200893	0.027337624
GCST90274765	GCST90200898	0.018768757
GCST90274765	GCST90200960	0.012069205
GCST90274765	GCST90200917	0.005249355
GCST90274765	GCST90200922	0.015715172
GCST90274765	GCST90200867	0.030066138
GCST90274765	GCST90200887	0.032634729
GCST90274765	GCST90200889	0.03883206
GCST90274765	GCST90200234	0.041810453
GCST90274765	GCST90200790	0.032424692
GCST90274765	GCST90200811	0.040295942
GCST90274765	GCST90200826	0.042064565

**Plasma proteins associated with primary
osteoarthropathy outcomes**

id	pvalue
GCST90200160	0.008202191
GCST90200660	0.016163049
GCST90199961	0.002000619
GCST90201000	0.00681054
GCST90199927	0.002635765
GCST90200573	0.006030538
GCST90200758	1.04E-05
GCST90200315	0.011376594
GCST90200893	0.004438928
GCST90200922	0.048265546

Cytokines	n S N P	Beta	P	Or	Or(95%CI)	Q_pval	Steige r_pval	MR- PRES SO_p val	MR Egger _pval
Glycine to phosphate ratio							0.042	0.443	0.832
MR Egger	34	0.099	0.222	1.104	0.945-1.29	0.398			
Weighted median	34	0.149	0.012	1.161	1.033-1.305				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.084	0.042	1.088	1.003-1.18	0.444			
Simple mode	34	0.172	0.172	1.187	0.933-1.511				
Weighted mode	34	0.193	0.036	1.213	1.02-1.444				
Choline to taurocholate ratio							0.04	0.305	0.533
MR Egger	34	0.047	0.591	1.048	0.886-1.239	0.311			
Weighted median	34	0.072	0.261	1.075	0.948-1.219				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.092	0.04	1.097	1.004-1.198	0.337			
Simple mode	34	0.121	0.443	1.128	0.832-1.531				
Weighted mode	34	-0.07	0.54	0.929	0.737-1.172				
Thyroxine to taurocholate ratio							0.032	0.137	0.476
MR Egger	34	0.047	0.61	1.048	0.877-1.252	0.163			
Weighted median	34	0.061	0.36	1.063	0.933-1.21				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.102	0.032	1.108	1.009-1.216	0.176			
Simple mode	34	0.131	0.346	1.14	0.871-1.492				
Weighted mode	34	-0.07	0.548	0.934	0.749-1.164				
Picolinoylglycine							0.042	0.859	0.557
MR Egger	34	-0.12	0.123	0.885	0.762-1.029	0.835			
Weighted median	34	-0.07	0.231	0.929	0.823-1.048				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.042	0.92	0.85-0.997	0.854			
Simple mode	34	-0.18	0.115	0.832	0.666-1.04				
Weighted mode	34	-0.11	0.171	0.893	0.762-1.046				
Cholesterol to taurocholate ratio							0.039	0.235	0.596
MR Egger	34	0.056	0.533	1.057	0.889-1.257	0.22			
Weighted median	34	0.017	0.789	1.018	0.896-1.155				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.096	0.039	1.101	1.005-1.205	0.246			
Simple mode	34	-0.01	0.936	0.989	0.751-1.302				
Weighted mode	34	-0.06	0.557	0.944	0.78-1.143				
Cholesterol to cortisol ratio							0.033	0.577	0.451
MR Egger	34	0.134	0.084	1.144	0.987-1.326	0.536			
Weighted median	34	0.05	0.412	1.051	0.933-1.185				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.086	0.033	1.089	1.007-1.178	0.556			
Simple mode	34	-0.01	0.91	0.987	0.789-1.235				
Weighted mode	34	0.014	0.861	1.014	0.869-1.182				
Adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP) to isoleucine ratio							0.03	0.335	0.274
MR Egger	34	0.017	0.834	1.017	0.87-1.189	0.352			
Weighted median	34	0.115	0.065	1.122	0.993-1.267				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.092	0.03	1.096	1.009-1.191	0.34			
Simple mode	34	0.12	0.253	1.127	0.921-1.38				
Weighted mode	34	0.102	0.237	1.107	0.938-1.307				
Alpha-ketobutyrate to pyruvate ratio							0.016	0.66	0.46
MR Egger	34	-0.15	0.064	0.86	0.737-1.003	0.605			
Weighted median	34	-0.1	0.103	0.902	0.797-1.021				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.016	0.904	0.833-0.981	0.626			
Simple mode	34	-0.09	0.4	0.911	0.735-1.129				
Weighted mode	34	-0.1	0.262	0.908	0.769-1.072				
Alpha-ketobutyrate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio							0.005	0.363	0.411
MR Egger	34	-0.18	0.037	0.837	0.713-0.982	0.326			
Weighted median	34	-0.15	0.02	0.861	0.759-0.977				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.12	0.005	0.886	0.814-0.965	0.338			
Simple mode	34	-0.12	0.302	0.886	0.706-1.111				

Weighted mode	34	-0.13	0.115	0.874	0.743-1.029				
Choline phosphate to phosphoethanolamine ratio							0.012	0.265	0.995
MR Egger	34	-0.11	0.201	0.895	0.758-1.057	0.184			
Weighted median	34	-0.14	0.033	0.871	0.767-0.989				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.012	0.895	0.82-0.976	0.218			
Simple mode	34	-0.17	0.136	0.846	0.682-1.048				
Weighted mode	34	-0.15	0.061	0.858	0.735-1.002				
Citrulline to phosphate ratio							0.019	0.597	0.658
MR Egger	34	0.066	0.391	1.069	0.92-1.241	0.548			
Weighted median	34	0.138	0.026	1.148	1.017-1.295				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.095	0.019	1.1	1.016-1.191	0.587			
Simple mode	34	0.061	0.64	1.063	0.824-1.373				
Weighted mode	34	0.132	0.118	1.141	0.971-1.341				
Taurine to cysteine ratio							0.027	0.678	0.67
MR Egger	34	0.117	0.134	1.124	0.968-1.306	0.61			
Weighted median	34	0.031	0.614	1.032	0.914-1.165				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.089	0.027	1.094	1.01-1.184	0.649			
Simple mode	34	0.036	0.763	1.036	0.824-1.304				
Weighted mode	34	0.032	0.698	1.033	0.878-1.215				
X-12816							0.044	0.209	0.693
MR Egger	34	0.079	0.478	1.082	0.872-1.342	0.15			
Weighted median	34	0.099	0.235	1.104	0.938-1.301				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.116	0.044	1.123	1.003-1.257	0.174			
Simple mode	34	0.02	0.9	1.02	0.746-1.395				
Weighted mode	34	0.055	0.604	1.057	0.859-1.301				
X-07765							0.013	0.214	0.995
MR Egger	34	-0.11	0.206	0.896	0.758-1.059	0.221			
Weighted median	34	-0.08	0.196	0.922	0.815-1.043				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.013	0.896	0.821-0.977	0.259			
Simple mode	34	-0.09	0.573	0.917	0.681-1.235				
Weighted mode	34	0.009	0.936	1.009	0.811-1.255				
Beta-hydroxyisovalerate							8E-04	0.586	0.806
MR Egger	34	-0.12	0.126	0.888	0.766-1.03	0.543			
Weighted median	34	-0.11	0.074	0.897	0.796-1.01				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.13	8E-04	0.874	0.808-0.945	0.59			
Simple mode	34	-0.24	0.05	0.783	0.619-0.991				
Weighted mode	34	-0.13	0.137	0.878	0.743-1.038				
Gamma-glutamylhistidine							0.032	0.601	0.055
MR Egger	34	-0.22	0.008	0.801	0.686-0.934	0.745			
Weighted median	34	-0.14	0.028	0.87	0.768-0.985				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.032	0.914	0.843-0.992	0.598			
Simple mode	34	-0.17	0.166	0.843	0.666-1.068				
Weighted mode	34	-0.16	0.068	0.852	0.722-1.006				
2-aminobutyrate							0.01	0.855	0.894
MR Egger	34	-0.1	0.218	0.906	0.777-1.057	0.805			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.168	0.914	0.805-1.039				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.01	0.898	0.828-0.974	0.839			
Simple mode	34	-0.18	0.12	0.835	0.67-1.042				
Weighted mode	34	-0.13	0.141	0.876	0.737-1.041				
X-26054							0.026	0.139	0.128
MR Egger	34	-0.21	0.016	0.809	0.687-0.953	0.19			
Weighted median	34	-0.19	0.001	0.823	0.732-0.925				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.026	0.904	0.827-0.988	0.141			
Simple mode	34	-0.29	0.055	0.75	0.565-0.996				
Weighted mode	34	-0.28	0.017	0.753	0.604-0.94				
X-12847							0.02	0.375	0.067
MR Egger	34	-0.23	0.007	0.792	0.676-0.928	0.469			
Weighted median	34	-0.15	0.028	0.863	0.758-0.984				

Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.02	0.902	0.827-0.984	0.35			
Simple mode	34	-0.16	0.192	0.855	0.68-1.076				
Weighted mode	34	-0.16	0.07	0.855	0.726-1.008				
X-12731							0.018	0.24	0.337
MR Egger	34	0.043	0.669	1.044	0.858-1.27	0.248			
Weighted median	34	0.143	0.054	1.154	0.998-1.334				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.125	0.018	1.134	1.022-1.258	0.247			
Simple mode	34	0.244	0.13	1.277	0.938-1.739				
Weighted mode	34	0.154	0.192	1.167	0.93-1.464				
X-16964							0.048	0.58	0.37
MR Egger	34	0.022	0.782	1.022	0.875-1.194	0.535			
Weighted median	34	0.087	0.165	1.091	0.965-1.233				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.083	0.048	1.087	1.001-1.18	0.543			
Simple mode	34	0.044	0.715	1.045	0.826-1.322				
Weighted mode	34	0.078	0.373	1.081	0.913-1.281				
Indolebutyrate							0.043	0.536	0.777
MR Egger	34	0.088	0.415	1.092	0.886-1.345	0.462			
Weighted median	34	0.106	0.205	1.112	0.944-1.309				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.114	0.043	1.12	1.003-1.251	0.508			
Simple mode	34	0.171	0.277	1.187	0.876-1.608				
Weighted mode	34	0.114	0.315	1.12	0.901-1.393				
Carnitine C5:1							0.025	0.137	0.051
MR Egger	34	-0.25	0.006	0.78	0.661-0.919	0.227			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.183	0.917	0.807-1.042				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.025	0.901	0.822-0.987	0.125			
Simple mode	34	-0.05	0.678	0.953	0.762-1.193				
Weighted mode	34	-0.09	0.34	0.918	0.771-1.092				
Citrulline to dimethylarginine (SDMA + ADMA) ratio							0.006	0.392	0.409
MR Egger	34	0.172	0.039	1.188	1.015-1.389	0.394			
Weighted median	34	0.127	0.042	1.135	1.005-1.282				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.115	0.006	1.122	1.033-1.219	0.408			
Simple mode	34	0.076	0.57	1.079	0.833-1.397				
Weighted mode	34	0.148	0.09	1.159	0.982-1.368				
Glycine to serine ratio							0.012	0.869	0.868
MR Egger	34	0.114	0.15	1.12	0.963-1.303	0.822			
Weighted median	34	0.095	0.119	1.1	0.976-1.24				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.103	0.012	1.108	1.023-1.201	0.853			
Simple mode	34	0.101	0.358	1.106	0.895-1.369				
Weighted mode	34	0.108	0.201	1.114	0.947-1.309				
Sphingosine to phosphate ratio							0.025	0.08	0.563
MR Egger	34	0.064	0.502	1.066	0.887-1.28	0.067			
Weighted median	34	0.145	0.03	1.157	1.014-1.319				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.11	0.025	1.116	1.014-1.229	0.076			
Simple mode	34	0.119	0.369	1.126	0.872-1.455				
Weighted mode	34	0.136	0.166	1.146	0.949-1.383				
Aspartate to glutamate ratio							0.006	0.967	0.818
MR Egger	34	0.095	0.216	1.1	0.949-1.275	0.959			
Weighted median	34	0.072	0.208	1.075	0.961-1.203				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.11	0.006	1.116	1.032-1.207	0.969			
Simple mode	34	0.037	0.745	1.038	0.83-1.298				
Weighted mode	34	0.03	0.738	1.03	0.867-1.223				
Phosphate to phosphoethanolamine ratio							0.007	0.563	0.406
MR Egger	34	-0.06	0.471	0.945	0.812-1.1	0.487			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.157	0.911	0.801-1.036				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.007	0.894	0.825-0.969	0.501			
Simple mode	34	-0.08	0.488	0.926	0.748-1.147				
Weighted mode	34	-0.1	0.236	0.906	0.773-1.063				
X-18935							0.001	0.039	0.528

MR Egger	34	-0.28	0.032	0.754	0.59-0.965	0.023			
Weighted median	34	-0.28	0.001	0.759	0.642-0.897				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.21	0.001	0.807	0.709-0.918	0.027			
Simple mode	34	-0.37	0.013	0.689	0.521-0.911				
Weighted mode	34	-0.33	0.003	0.721	0.591-0.879				
X-19299							0.015	0.837	0.05
MR Egger	34	0.274	0.005	1.315	1.1-1.572	0.914			
Weighted median	34	0.116	0.099	1.123	0.979-1.289				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.117	0.015	1.124	1.023-1.236	0.807			
Simple mode	34	0.198	0.125	1.219	0.953-1.559				
Weighted mode	34	0.143	0.155	1.154	0.952-1.4				
X-21319							0.028	0.238	0.396
MR Egger	34	-0.16	0.068	0.852	0.721-1.006	0.228			
Weighted median	34	-0.05	0.458	0.952	0.836-1.084				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.028	0.906	0.83-0.99	0.236			
Simple mode	34	-0.12	0.321	0.883	0.693-1.125				
Weighted mode	34	-0.07	0.456	0.936	0.787-1.112				
1-palmitoyl-2-stearoyl-gpc (16:0/18:0)							0.018	0.622	0.872
MR Egger	34	0.087	0.271	1.091	0.937-1.27	0.581			
Weighted median	34	0.124	0.054	1.132	0.998-1.284				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.098	0.018	1.103	1.017-1.196	0.629			
Simple mode	34	-0.07	0.622	0.933	0.71-1.226				
Weighted mode	34	0.221	0.028	1.247	1.033-1.506				
Histidine betaine (hercynine)							0.035	0.948	0.898
MR Egger	34	-0.1	0.228	0.904	0.769-1.062	0.93			
Weighted median	34	-0.13	0.053	0.881	0.775-1.002				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.035	0.912	0.837-0.993	0.946			
Simple mode	34	0.087	0.522	1.091	0.838-1.42				
Weighted mode	34	-0.16	0.101	0.854	0.71-1.026				
Sulfate							0.022	0.107	0.794
MR Egger	34	-0.12	0.166	0.883	0.744-1.049	0.109			
Weighted median	34	-0.04	0.506	0.958	0.844-1.087				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.022	0.9	0.823-0.985	0.131			
Simple mode	34	-0.31	0.052	0.733	0.543-0.991				
Weighted mode	34	0.059	0.622	1.061	0.839-1.342				
Sulfate of piperine metabolite C16H19NO3 (3)							0.007	0.85	0.423
MR Egger	34	-0.17	0.041	0.843	0.721-0.987	0.817			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.152	0.911	0.802-1.035				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.12	0.007	0.891	0.82-0.968	0.826			
Simple mode	34	-0.19	0.112	0.83	0.664-1.038				
Weighted mode	34	-0.11	0.213	0.895	0.755-1.062				
2-linoleoylglycerol (18:2)							0.029	0.788	0.735
MR Egger	34	-0.13	0.158	0.879	0.738-1.047	0.748			
Weighted median	34	-0.12	0.114	0.889	0.768-1.029				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.029	0.902	0.822-0.99	0.783			
Simple mode	34	-0	0.981	0.997	0.759-1.309				
Weighted mode	34	-0.06	0.579	0.945	0.777-1.15				
1-linoleoylglycerol (18:2)							0.03	0.967	0.506
MR Egger	34	-0.05	0.567	0.956	0.82-1.114	0.962			
Weighted median	34	-0.1	0.13	0.908	0.802-1.029				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.03	0.914	0.843-0.992	0.967			
Simple mode	34	0.01	0.929	1.011	0.805-1.268				
Weighted mode	34	-0.06	0.522	0.945	0.795-1.122				
Glycoursodeoxycholic acid sulfate (1)							0.044	0.662	0.121
MR Egger	34	-0.02	0.781	0.976	0.823-1.157	0.724			
Weighted median	34	0.054	0.443	1.055	0.92-1.211				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.093	0.044	1.097	1.002-1.201	0.647			
Simple mode	34	0.034	0.797	1.035	0.798-1.342				

Weighted mode	34	0.038	0.677	1.039	0.87-1.241				
Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (5)							0.004	0.422	0.056
MR Egger	34	-0.28	0.003	0.755	0.636-0.896	0.547			
Weighted median	34	-0.14	0.067	0.872	0.752-1.01				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.13	0.004	0.874	0.797-0.959	0.403			
Simple mode	34	-0.14	0.279	0.866	0.67-1.119				
Weighted mode	34	-0.14	0.183	0.866	0.704-1.065				
Piperine							0.001	0.822	0.27
MR Egger	34	-0.21	0.012	0.812	0.696-0.946	0.827			
Weighted median	34	-0.15	0.024	0.864	0.761-0.981				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.13	0.001	0.874	0.806-0.949	0.812			
Simple mode	34	-0.17	0.113	0.841	0.682-1.036				
Weighted mode	34	-0.16	0.061	0.849	0.719-1.002				
1-myristoyl-2-palmitoyl-gpc (14:0/16:0)							0.02	0.158	0.627
MR Egger	34	0.071	0.424	1.073	0.904-1.274	0.128			
Weighted median	34	0.113	0.081	1.12	0.986-1.271				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.107	0.02	1.113	1.017-1.218	0.147			
Simple mode	34	0.077	0.523	1.08	0.856-1.362				
Weighted mode	34	0.088	0.327	1.092	0.918-1.299				
1-stearoyl-2-oleoyl-GPS (18:0/18:1)							0.035	0.765	0.665
MR Egger	34	0.059	0.46	1.061	0.909-1.238	0.722			
Weighted median	34	0.095	0.14	1.1	0.969-1.247				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.088	0.035	1.092	1.006-1.185	0.756			
Simple mode	34	0.112	0.288	1.118	0.913-1.37				
Weighted mode	34	0.101	0.228	1.107	0.941-1.301				
10-undecenoate (11:1n1)							0.043	0.71	0.834
MR Egger	34	-0.1	0.22	0.907	0.779-1.057	0.688			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.133	0.915	0.814-1.027				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.043	0.92	0.849-0.997	0.73			
Simple mode	34	-0.03	0.835	0.975	0.77-1.234				
Weighted mode	34	-0.09	0.321	0.918	0.778-1.084				
Citrate to taurocholate ratio							0.048	0.215	0.433
MR Egger	34	0.033	0.713	1.033	0.869-1.228	0.23			
Weighted median	34	0.065	0.286	1.067	0.947-1.202				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.092	0.048	1.096	1.001-1.201	0.242			
Simple mode	34	0.065	0.627	1.068	0.822-1.386				
Weighted mode	34	0.01	0.915	1.01	0.838-1.218				
Phosphoethanolamine to choline ratio							0.036	0.163	0.874
MR Egger	34	0.083	0.343	1.087	0.917-1.288	0.122			
Weighted median	34	0.076	0.227	1.079	0.954-1.221				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.095	0.036	1.1	1.006-1.202	0.147			
Simple mode	34	0.109	0.339	1.115	0.895-1.39				
Weighted mode	34	0.077	0.337	1.08	0.925-1.26				
Adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP) to urate ratio							0.044	0.11	0.337
MR Egger	34	0.021	0.809	1.021	0.862-1.209	0.096			
Weighted median	34	0.031	0.617	1.032	0.913-1.165				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.092	0.044	1.097	1.003-1.199	0.094			
Simple mode	34	0.046	0.665	1.047	0.853-1.285				
Weighted mode	34	0.037	0.623	1.038	0.895-1.203				
4-methyl-2-oxopentanoate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ra							0.018	0.931	0.97
MR Egger	34	-0.1	0.207	0.907	0.783-1.052	0.908			
Weighted median	34	-0.11	0.062	0.895	0.796-1.006				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.018	0.91	0.841-0.984	0.928			
Simple mode	34	-0.05	0.681	0.955	0.766-1.189				
Weighted mode	34	-0.09	0.27	0.912	0.777-1.071				
3-methyl-2-oxovalerate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio							0.046	0.719	0.997
MR Egger	34	-0.08	0.296	0.922	0.794-1.071	0.656			
Weighted median	34	-0.07	0.255	0.935	0.833-1.05				

Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.046	0.922	0.852-0.999	0.702			
Simple mode	34	-0.2	0.119	0.816	0.637-1.046				
Weighted mode	34	-0.1	0.285	0.905	0.756-1.083				
Threonine to alpha-ketobutyrate ratio							0.014	0.18	0.254
MR Egger	34	0.2	0.028	1.222	1.03-1.449	0.178			
Weighted median	34	0.124	0.052	1.132	0.999-1.283				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.114	0.014	1.121	1.023-1.228	0.164			
Simple mode	34	0.13	0.273	1.139	0.906-1.433				
Weighted mode	34	0.134	0.142	1.144	0.96-1.363				
Serine to threonine ratio							0.038	0.895	0.603
MR Egger	34	-0.12	0.132	0.888	0.764-1.032	0.86			
Weighted median	34	-0.08	0.189	0.927	0.828-1.038				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.038	0.919	0.849-0.996	0.879			
Simple mode	34	-0.13	0.266	0.881	0.708-1.097				
Weighted mode	34	-0.07	0.349	0.928	0.796-1.082				
3-hydroxyhexanoate							0.019	0.831	0.198
MR Egger	34	-0.18	0.024	0.836	0.721-0.97	0.86			
Weighted median	34	-0.15	0.011	0.863	0.77-0.966				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.019	0.91	0.841-0.984	0.829			
Simple mode	34	-0.19	0.133	0.828	0.651-1.053				
Weighted mode	34	-0.2	0.028	0.821	0.693-0.972				
Methionine sulfone							0.042	0.68	0.115
MR Egger	34	-0.18	0.02	0.836	0.724-0.965	0.723			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.14	0.915	0.813-1.029				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.042	0.924	0.856-0.997	0.641			
Simple mode	34	-0.07	0.53	0.932	0.75-1.158				
Weighted mode	34	-0.1	0.241	0.907	0.773-1.065				
N-formylanthranilic acid							0.009	0.648	0.113
MR Egger	34	-0.22	0.009	0.8	0.682-0.937	0.709			
Weighted median	34	-0.2	0.003	0.822	0.721-0.936				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.009	0.894	0.822-0.972	0.625			
Simple mode	34	-0.25	0.072	0.778	0.598-1.013				
Weighted mode	34	-0.22	0.018	0.802	0.674-0.955				
X-25957							0.041	0.652	0.348
MR Egger	34	-0.02	0.785	0.978	0.832-1.149	0.646			
Weighted median	34	-0.11	0.092	0.896	0.788-1.018				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.041	0.914	0.839-0.997	0.648			
Simple mode	34	-0.06	0.641	0.941	0.731-1.212				
Weighted mode	34	-0.13	0.196	0.882	0.733-1.063				
X-24949							0.003	0.797	0.371
MR Egger	34	-0.2	0.025	0.822	0.698-0.967	0.792			
Weighted median	34	-0.15	0.035	0.861	0.75-0.99				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.13	0.003	0.876	0.804-0.955	0.795			
Simple mode	34	-0.19	0.187	0.829	0.632-1.089				
Weighted mode	34	-0.16	0.116	0.851	0.699-1.035				
X-24736							0.029	0.587	0.432
MR Egger	34	-0.05	0.635	0.953	0.784-1.159	0.578			
Weighted median	34	-0.18	0.03	0.834	0.708-0.983				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.12	0.029	0.891	0.803-0.989	0.595			
Simple mode	34	-0.16	0.315	0.854	0.631-1.156				
Weighted mode	34	-0.19	0.063	0.825	0.677-1.003				
1-linoleoyl-GPG (18:2)							0.025	0.956	0.195
MR Egger	34	-0.18	0.028	0.834	0.715-0.973	0.965			
Weighted median	34	-0.13	0.039	0.878	0.775-0.994				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.025	0.911	0.84-0.989	0.95			
Simple mode	34	-0.08	0.517	0.926	0.736-1.165				
Weighted mode	34	-0.18	0.04	0.832	0.703-0.985				
2s,3R-dihydroxybutyrate							0.021	0.861	0.311

MR Egger	34	-0.15	0.044	0.863	0.752-0.99	0.846			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.098	0.912	0.818-1.017				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.021	0.917	0.853-0.987	0.84			
Simple mode	34	-0.09	0.334	0.911	0.757-1.097				
Weighted mode	34	-0.11	0.18	0.897	0.768-1.048				
5-(galactosylhydroxy)-L-lysine							0.03	0.084	0.202
MR Egger	34	-0.22	0.031	0.803	0.664-0.971	0.081			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.198	0.91	0.789-1.05				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.03	0.894	0.807-0.989	0.065			
Simple mode	34	-0.19	0.168	0.826	0.633-1.078				
Weighted mode	34	-0.13	0.155	0.878	0.736-1.046				
Androstenediol (3alpha, 17alpha) monosulfate (3)							0.032	0.307	0.802
MR Egger	34	-0.07	0.369	0.935	0.808-1.081	0.225			
Weighted median	34	-0.02	0.782	0.985	0.884-1.097				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.032	0.92	0.853-0.993	0.261			
Simple mode	34	-0.1	0.327	0.907	0.749-1.099				
Weighted mode	34	-0.01	0.879	0.989	0.853-1.145				
5alpha-androstan-3alpha,17alpha-diol monosulfate							0.006	0.165	0.231
MR Egger	34	-0.25	0.017	0.782	0.646-0.948	0.204			
Weighted median	34	-0.11	0.128	0.892	0.769-1.034				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.14	0.006	0.866	0.781-0.96	0.184			
Simple mode	34	-0.14	0.373	0.867	0.637-1.181				
Weighted mode	34	-0.06	0.568	0.94	0.762-1.16				
Allantoin							0.017	0.957	0.478
MR Egger	34	-0.05	0.517	0.951	0.819-1.105	0.959			
Weighted median	34	-0.08	0.179	0.926	0.827-1.036				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.017	0.908	0.839-0.983	0.963			
Simple mode	34	-0.18	0.138	0.833	0.659-1.054				
Weighted mode	34	0.008	0.919	1.008	0.858-1.185				
Picolinate							0.025	0.682	0.412
MR Egger	34	-0.16	0.067	0.854	0.725-1.005	0.659			
Weighted median	34	-0.08	0.27	0.924	0.804-1.063				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.025	0.905	0.83-0.988	0.671			
Simple mode	34	-0.17	0.19	0.844	0.658-1.082				
Weighted mode	34	-0.09	0.34	0.912	0.757-1.099				
Phosphoethanolamine							0.031	0.215	0.432
MR Egger	34	0.04	0.646	1.04	0.88-1.231	0.176			
Weighted median	34	0.037	0.54	1.038	0.921-1.17				
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.098	0.031	1.102	1.009-1.205	0.185			
Simple mode	34	0.063	0.588	1.065	0.851-1.331				
Weighted mode	34	0.049	0.588	1.05	0.882-1.251				
5-oxoproline							0.007	0.749	0.837
MR Egger	34	-0.1	0.221	0.907	0.779-1.057	0.733			
Weighted median	34	-0.07	0.251	0.934	0.83-1.05				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.007	0.895	0.825-0.971	0.772			
Simple mode	34	-0.07	0.587	0.933	0.729-1.195				
Weighted mode	34	-0.03	0.766	0.973	0.811-1.166				
Pantothenate							0.046	0.559	0.383
MR Egger	34	-0.02	0.759	0.977	0.84-1.135	0.55			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.145	0.916	0.813-1.031				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.046	0.922	0.851-0.999	0.56			
Simple mode	34	-0.16	0.214	0.856	0.674-1.089				
Weighted mode	34	-0.1	0.219	0.905	0.775-1.058				
Bilirubin degradation product, C16H18N2O5 (1)							0.046	0.148	0.81
MR Egger	34	-0.11	0.221	0.896	0.754-1.065	0.137			
Weighted median	34	-0.03	0.626	0.97	0.859-1.096				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.046	0.912	0.833-0.999	0.164			
Simple mode	34	-0.09	0.42	0.912	0.732-1.137				

Weighted mode	34	-0.02	0.825	0.982	0.839-1.15				
Bilirubin degradation product, C17H20N2O5 (1)							0.043	0.698	0.136
MR Egger	34	0.017	0.826	1.017	0.876-1.182	0.8			
Weighted median	34	-0.04	0.558	0.965	0.856-1.087				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.043	0.921	0.851-0.997	0.737			
Simple mode	34	-0.09	0.483	0.914	0.713-1.172				
Weighted mode	34	0.054	0.539	1.056	0.89-1.252				
Cis-3,4-methyleneheptanoylcarnitine							0.019	0.195	0.492
MR Egger	34	-0.16	0.077	0.856	0.724-1.011	0.169			
Weighted median	34	-0.08	0.223	0.923	0.812-1.05				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.019	0.9	0.824-0.983	0.183			
Simple mode	34	-0.11	0.341	0.895	0.714-1.122				
Weighted mode	34	-0.09	0.271	0.911	0.775-1.072				
Bilirubin degradation product, C17H20N2O5 (2)							0.04	0.688	0.141
MR Egger	34	0.014	0.851	1.015	0.874-1.178	0.764			
Weighted median	34	-0.04	0.523	0.963	0.857-1.081				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.04	0.92	0.85-0.996	0.702			
Simple mode	34	-0.1	0.465	0.909	0.707-1.17				
Weighted mode	34	0.062	0.449	1.064	0.907-1.248				
Cis 3,4-methyleneheptanoate							0.006	0.507	0.717
MR Egger	34	-0.14	0.091	0.872	0.748-1.017	0.433			
Weighted median	34	-0.11	0.081	0.894	0.787-1.014				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.006	0.894	0.824-0.969	0.476			
Simple mode	34	-0.07	0.538	0.931	0.744-1.165				
Weighted mode	34	-0.09	0.287	0.91	0.767-1.08				
Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (4)							0.017	0.447	0.248
MR Egger	34	-0.18	0.03	0.835	0.714-0.976	0.464			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.17	0.915	0.807-1.039				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.017	0.904	0.831-0.982	0.446			
Simple mode	34	-0.06	0.632	0.94	0.733-1.207				
Weighted mode	34	-0.07	0.456	0.937	0.791-1.11				
Sulfate of piperine metabolite C18H21NO3 (1)							0.048	0.473	0.291
MR Egger	34	-0.01	0.892	0.989	0.839-1.164	0.477			
Weighted median	34	-0.06	0.391	0.946	0.833-1.074				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.048	0.916	0.84-0.999	0.47			
Simple mode	34	-0.09	0.522	0.912	0.691-1.204				
Weighted mode	34	-0.05	0.598	0.952	0.793-1.142				
Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (3)							0.038	0.129	0.128
MR Egger	34	-0.24	0.02	0.79	0.655-0.954	0.19			
Weighted median	34	-0.09	0.235	0.912	0.784-1.062				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.11	0.038	0.897	0.81-0.994	0.141			
Simple mode	34	-0.12	0.43	0.891	0.671-1.183				
Weighted mode	34	-0.1	0.334	0.903	0.737-1.107				
X-23680							0.02	0.547	0.729
MR Egger	34	-0.12	0.135	0.889	0.765-1.033	0.47			
Weighted median	34	-0.03	0.609	0.97	0.862-1.091				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.02	0.91	0.84-0.985	0.514			
Simple mode	34	-0.01	0.964	0.995	0.795-1.245				
Weighted mode	34	-0.02	0.812	0.981	0.836-1.15				
X-21845							0.024	0.439	0.663
MR Egger	34	-0.09	0.423	0.918	0.747-1.128	0.376			
Weighted median	34	-0.2	0.015	0.818	0.696-0.961				
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.12	0.024	0.883	0.793-0.983	0.414			
Simple mode	34	-0.18	0.229	0.839	0.634-1.111				
Weighted mode	34	-0.18	0.1	0.839	0.685-1.028				
X-21607							0.031	0.503	0.392
MR Egger	34	-0.15	0.069	0.863	0.74-1.006	0.469			
Weighted median	34	-0.06	0.35	0.946	0.841-1.063				

Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.031	0.914	0.842-0.992	0.482				
Simple mode	34	-0.03	0.833	0.972	0.746-1.266					
Weighted mode	34	-0.07	0.469	0.934	0.777-1.122					
X-23659								0.012	0.702	0.112
MR Egger	34	-0.2	0.01	0.82	0.711-0.946	0.76				
Weighted median	34	-0.07	0.219	0.929	0.826-1.045					
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.012	0.907	0.841-0.979	0.679				
Simple mode	34	0.02	0.857	1.021	0.818-1.273					
Weighted mode	34	-0.08	0.317	0.923	0.79-1.078					
Citrulline								0.022	0.793	0.762
MR Egger	34	0.075	0.344	1.077	0.925-1.255	0.749				
Weighted median	34	0.056	0.384	1.057	0.933-1.198					
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.095	0.022	1.099	1.014-1.192	0.785				
Simple mode	34	-0.02	0.887	0.984	0.791-1.224					
Weighted mode	34	0.051	0.579	1.052	0.881-1.257					
Taurocholic acid								0.03	0.358	0.227
MR Egger	34	-0.01	0.908	0.991	0.845-1.161	0.451				
Weighted median	34	-0.06	0.378	0.945	0.832-1.072					
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.09	0.03	0.91	0.836-0.991	0.426				
Simple mode	34	-0.04	0.795	0.962	0.72-1.285					
Weighted mode	34	0.067	0.549	1.069	0.861-1.327					
Sphingosine								0.027	0.148	0.551
MR Egger	34	0.059	0.518	1.061	0.888-1.268	0.113				
Weighted median	34	0.081	0.231	1.084	0.95-1.237					
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.106	0.027	1.112	1.012-1.221	0.127				
Simple mode	34	0.134	0.303	1.143	0.89-1.468					
Weighted mode	34	0.08	0.37	1.084	0.911-1.289					
Guanidinoacetate								0.006	0.829	0.656
MR Egger	34	0.138	0.073	1.148	0.992-1.327	0.825				
Weighted median	34	0.142	0.016	1.153	1.027-1.294					
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.109	0.006	1.116	1.033-1.205	0.85				
Simple mode	34	0.072	0.526	1.075	0.863-1.338					
Weighted mode	34	0.175	0.049	1.191	1.007-1.408					
S-1-pyrroline-5-carboxylate								0.041	0.467	0.21
MR Egger	34	####	1	1	0.858-1.166	0.522				
Weighted median	34	-0.07	0.238	0.93	0.824-1.049					
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.08	0.041	0.919	0.847-0.997	0.49				
Simple mode	34	-0.17	0.181	0.843	0.659-1.077					
Weighted mode	34	-0.01	0.886	0.986	0.818-1.189					
Sphinganine								0.013	0.091	0.998
MR Egger	34	0.125	0.206	1.133	0.937-1.369	0.077				
Weighted median	34	0.062	0.364	1.064	0.93-1.217					
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.125	0.013	1.133	1.026-1.251	0.096				
Simple mode	34	0.009	0.95	1.009	0.77-1.322					
Weighted mode	34	-0	0.975	0.995	0.75-1.322					
Octadecadienedioate (C18:2-DC)								0.023	0.402	0.836
MR Egger	34	-0.11	0.18	0.895	0.764-1.049	0.314				
Weighted median	34	-0.12	0.069	0.89	0.786-1.009					
Inverse variance weighte	34	-0.1	0.023	0.908	0.836-0.987	0.356				
Simple mode	34	-0.22	0.096	0.806	0.63-1.032					
Weighted mode	34	-0.12	0.238	0.889	0.735-1.077					
Trans-2-hexenoylglycine								0.015	0.263	0.342
MR Egger	34	0.042	0.641	1.043	0.876-1.241	0.258				
Weighted median	34	0.093	0.149	1.098	0.967-1.246					
Inverse variance weighte	34	0.114	0.015	1.121	1.022-1.23	0.258				
Simple mode	34	0.255	0.104	1.29	0.957-1.74					
Weighted mode	34	-0.03	0.802	0.975	0.798-1.19					

Glycine to phosphate ratio

Glycine to phosphate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Choline to taurocholate ratio

Choline to taurocholate ratio

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Thyroxine to taurocholate ratio

Thyroxine to taurocholate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Picolinoylglycine

Picolinoylglycine

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Cholesterol to taurocholate ratio

Cholesterol to taurocholate ratio

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Cholesterol to cortisol ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP) to isoleucine ratio

Adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP) to isoleucine ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Alpha-ketobutyrate to pyruvate ratio

Alpha-ketobutyrate to pyruvate ratio

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Alpha-ketobutyrate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio

Alpha-ketobutyrate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Choline phosphate to phosphoethanolamine ratio

Choline phosphate to phosphoethanolamine ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Citrulline to phosphate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-12816

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Taurine to cysteine ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-07765

Beta-hydroxyisovalerate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Gamma-glutamylhistidine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

2-aminobutyrate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-26054

X-12847

X-12731

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-16964

X-16964

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Indolebutyrate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Carnitine C5:1

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Citrulline to dimethylarginine (SDMA + ADMA) ratio

Citrulline to dimethylarginine (SDMA + ADMA) ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Glycine to serine ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Sphingosine to phosphate ratio

Sphingosine to phosphate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Aspartate to glutamate ratio

Phosphate to phosphoethanolamine ratio

Phosphate to phosphoethanolamine ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-18935

X-18935

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-19299

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-21319

1-palmitoyl-2-stearoyl-gpc (16:0/18:0)

1-palmitoyl-2-stearoyl-gpc (16:0/18:0)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Histidine betaine (hercynine)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Sulfate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Sulfate of piperine metabolite C16H19NO3

Sulfate of piperine metabolite C16H19NO3

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

2-linoleoylglycerol

1-linoleoylglycerol

Glycoursodeoxycholic acid sulfate (1)

Glycoursodeoxycholic acid sulfate (1)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3

Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Piperine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

1-myristoyl-2-palmitoyl-gpc

1-myristoyl-2-palmitoyl-gpc

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

1-stearoyl-2-oleoyl-GPS

10-undecenoate (11:1n1)

Citrate to taurocholate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Phosphoethanolamine to choline ratio

Adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP) to urate ratio

Adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP) to urate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

4-methyl-2-oxopentanoate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio

4-methyl-2-oxopentanoate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

3-methyl-2-oxovalerate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio

3-methyl-2-oxovalerate to 3-methyl-2-oxobutyrate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Threonine to alpha-ketobutyrate ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Serine to threonine ratio

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

3-hydroxyhexanoate

Methionine sulfone

N-formylanthranilic acid

X-25957

X-25957

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-24949

X-24949

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-24736

X-24736

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

1-linoleoyl-GPG

2s,3R-dihydroxybutyrate

2s,3R-dihydroxybutyrate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

5-(galactosylhydroxy)-L-lysine

5-(galactosylhydroxy)-L-lysine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Androstenediol (3alpha, 17alpha) monosulfate (3)

Androstenediol (3alpha, 17alpha) monosulfate (3)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

5alpha-androstan-3alpha,17alpha-diol monosulfate

5alpha-androstan-3alpha,17alpha-diol monosulfate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Allantoin

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Picolinate

Picolinate

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Phosphoethanolamine

5-oxoproline

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Pantothenate

Pantothenate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Bilirubin degradation product, C₁₆H₁₈N₂O₅ (1)

Bilirubin degradation product, C₁₆H₁₈N₂O₅ (1)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Bilirubin degradation product, C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₅ (1)

Bilirubin degradation product, C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₅ (1)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Cis-3,4-methyleneheptanoylcarnitine

Cis-3,4-methyleneheptanoylcarnitine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Bilirubin degradation product, C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₅ (2)

Bilirubin degradation product, C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₅ (2)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Cis 3,4-methyleneheptanoate

Cis 3,4-methyleneheptanoate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (4)

Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (4)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Sulfate of piperine metabolite C₁₈H₂₁NO₃ (1)

Sulfate of piperine metabolite C₁₈H₂₁NO₃ (1)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (3)

Glucuronide of piperine metabolite C17H21NO3 (3)

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-23680

X-23680

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-21845

X-21845

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-21607

X-21607

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

X-23659

X-23659

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Citrulline

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Taurocholic acid

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Sphingosine

Sphingosine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Guanidinoacetate

Guanidinoacetate

A

B

C

D

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

S-1-pyrroline-5-carboxylate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Sphinganine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Octadecadienedioate

Octadecadienedioate

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Trans-2-hexenoylglycine

Trans-2-hexenoylglycine

(A) Funnel plots (B) Scatter plots (C) Forest plots (D) Leave-one-out plots

Cytokines	nSNP	Beta	P	Or	Or(95%CI)
CCL19 on KNEEARTHROSIS					
MR Egger	36	-0.14951	0.002014375	0.861128	0.789-0.940
Weighted median	36	-0.12932	0.000429836	0.87869	0.818-0.944
Inverse variance weighted	36	-0.09834	0.000581255	0.906341	0.857-0.959
Simple mode	36	-0.15435	0.01484773	0.856971	0.762-0.964
Weighted mode	36	-0.142	1.32E-04	0.86762	0.813-0.926
KNEEARTHROSIS on CCL19					
MR Egger	28	0.087805	0.298819257	1.091775	0.928-1.284
Weighted median	28	-0.01999	0.653326853	0.980207	0.898-1.070
Inverse variance weighted	28	-0.0242	0.447486823	0.976095	0.917-1.039
Simple mode	28	-0.01292	0.871819782	0.987167	0.845-1.153
Weighted mode	28	0.006952	9.18E-01	1.006976	0.883-1.149
CCL 19 on Glycine to serine ratio					
MR Egger	34	0.113658	0.150279624	1.120369	0.963-1.303
Weighted median	34	0.095238	0.144996199	1.09992	0.968-1.250
Inverse variance weighted	34	0.102702	0.01212044	1.108162	1.023-1.201
Simple mode	34	0.101199	0.359153183	1.106496	0.894-1.370
Weighted mode	34	0.107621	2.25E-01	1.113626	0.939-1.321
Glycine to serine ratio on KNEEARTHROSIS					
MR Egger	25	0.099462	0.017692674	1.104576	1.023-1.192
Weighted median	25	0.106875	1.69E-05	1.112795	1.060-1.168
Inverse variance weighted	25	0.101983	1.04E-05	1.107365	1.058-1.159
Simple mode	25	0.107419	0.127155174	1.1134	0.974-1.272
Weighted mode	25	0.107419	1.51E-04	1.1134	1.062-1.167

Intermediary analysis

beta_all	-0.0983399
beta1	0.10270244
beta2	0.10198312
beta_intermediary effect	0.01047391
beta_direct effect	-0.1088138